

Numerical and Experimental Investigations on Cylindrical Shells Subjected to External Pressure

Esmail Azizi^{*,a}, Nariman Afzali^b, Natalie Stranghöner^b

University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures, Essen, Germany

^aesmaeil.azizi@uni-due.de

^bnariman.afzali@uni-due.de

^bnatalie.stranghoener@uni-due.de

ABSTRACT

Cylindrical shells are widely used in various engineering applications, such as pressure vessels, tanks, silos and pipelines, where they are subjected to external pressure that can significantly affect their structural performance. Understanding the buckling behaviour of cylindrical shells under external pressure is essential to their safe and reliable design.

The objective of the presented study was to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of numerical simulations in predicting the buckling behaviour of cylindrical shells under external pressure by comparing numerical results with experimental data. The numerical simulations were performed using the finite element program ANSYS, while the experimental tests were carried out on cylindrical shells under controlled external pressure.

The comparative analysis focuses on key parameters such as deformation, buckling, and failure modes. The experimental results of unstiffened and ring stiffened cylindrical shells are compared in terms of load-displacement curves and failure patterns. The discrepancies between numerical and experimental data are analysed, and the potential reasons of these discrepancies are discussed. The comparative analysis highlights the importance of considering various factors, such as material properties, geometric imperfections and boundary conditions, in order to improve the accuracy of numerical predictions.

The outcomes of the presented study contribute to enhancing the design and analysis methodologies given in the European design standards, e.g., EN 1993-1-6 and EN 1993-4-1, for designing cylindrical shells subjected to external pressure.

Keywords: External pressure, numerical and experimental results, European design standards

1 INTRODUCTION

Cylindrical shells are widely used as structural elements in various engineering applications such as tanks, silos, wind turbine towers, offshore platforms, and chimneys. One common failure mode for such structures, especially when they are empty or partially filled, is buckling under wind loading or vacuum caused by blocked vents. The European standard for shells EN 1993-1-6 (1) and the European Recommendation ECCS-EDR5 (2) allow replacing the unsymmetrical distribution of wind loading with an equivalent uniform external pressure for the buckling design check. This simplification facilitates the development of algebraic expressions, which often accurately represent the critical buckling load-bearing capacity of shell structures under complex, unsymmetrical circumferential loading.

In the past, shell structures were commonly made of structural steels or austenitic stainless steels with low yield strengths. However, high-strength structural and duplex stainless steels in accordance with EN 10088-4/-5 (3), (4) are increasingly being used, e.g. in biogas digesters, see *Fig. 1*. The reason

for this increasing application is that the use of high-strength structural and duplex stainless steels leads to a reduction in steel consumption, manufacturing and assembly costs. Nevertheless, an accurate prediction of the buckling strength of cylindrical shells is crucial for ensuring the structural integrity and safety of various engineering applications. The European design standards, e.g. EN 1993-1-6 (1), -4-1 (5) and -4-2 (6), are primarily intended for designing shell structures fabricated from carbon and stainless steels with low yield strengths. Therefore, they do not fully consider the particular impact of material behaviour of high-strength steels, such as the nonlinear response of duplex stainless steels below the 0.2% proof stress, potentially leading to inaccurate predictions of the load-bearing capacity. To address the limitation of existing design standards for high-strength steels, experimental and numerical investigations were systematically carried out on circumferentially loaded cylindrical shells made of duplex stainless steel.

Fig. 1. Biogas digester made of duplex stainless steel in the construction stage (© Weltec Biopower)

To significantly enhance the buckling capacity of medium-slender and thin-walled shell structures while minimizing material usage, longitudinal and ring stiffeners are often employed to ensure sufficient buckling resistance for these structures under strong wind or high axial pressure loads. To maximum the effectiveness, the stiffeners are strategically oriented to align with the direction of the buckling-inducing membrane pressure forces. In the case of extremely thin-walled liquid containers with a high r/t -ratio, for example, the external pressure causes often buckling, making ring stiffeners highly effective in enhancing the load-bearing capacity.

Stiffened shell structures can be generally categorized into three main types based on the critical load they are designed to resist: (i) longitudinally stiffened, (ii) ring-stiffened, and (iii) orthogonally stiffened cylindrical shells. These categories correspond to axial loading, external pressure, and combined loading, respectively. Furthermore, a thorough understanding of the various failure modes exhibited by cylindrical shells is essential for the design, analysis, and selection of appropriate stiffener configurations. The stiffened shell structures generally exhibit three different modes of failure:

- *Local buckling of shell: common failure mode of thick-walled cylinders or widely spaced stiffened cylindrical shells, see Fig. 2 a).*

- *Global buckling: common failure mode of thin-walled cylinders or closely spaced stiffened cylindrical shells, see Fig. 2 b).*

- *Local buckling of stiffeners: common failure mode of highly imperfect stiffeners (cylinders) and for ring stiffeners with a weak bending resistance.*

Fig. 2. Failure modes of ring-stiffened cylindrical shells under circumferential pressure

Current design standards, codes, and guidelines (e.g. (2), (7), (8)) for shell structures inadequately address the failure modes mentioned above. A significant limitation lies in their design rules for stiffened circular cylindrical shells. These rules often contain two deficiencies:

- *User-unfriendliness: The complexity of the design rules makes them difficult for engineers to apply effectively in practice.*
- *Incompleteness: Essential factors influencing buckling behaviour are not adequately considered. These factors include: (i) The combination of end boundary conditions for global buckling, (ii) the position of stiffeners (internal/external), and (iii) the dependence to the imperfection sensitivity on the shell/stiffener geometry.*

Despite a long history of research on the stability of steel shell structures, these limitations hinder the accurate prediction of the buckling strength of stiffened cylindrical shells.

In 1929, von Mises (9) derived a foundational equation for calculating the ideal critical buckling load of an unstiffened cylindrical shell under uniform external pressure. This equation served as the basis for further work by Windenburg/Trilling (10) and Batdorf (11) who developed analytical approaches for determining the ideal buckling pressure of shells under uniform circumferential stress. The influence of various boundary conditions on the ideal buckling pressure of unstiffened cylindrical shells was investigated by Schnell (12), Singer (13), Thielemann/Esslinger (14), Greiner (15), and Azizi/Stranghöner (16) among others. Donnell (17), Hutchinson (18), Knoedel et al. (19), and Azizi/Stranghöner (16) focused on the more realistic scenario of imperfect shells, aiming to estimate the buckling resistance of unstiffened cylindrical shells more accurately.

Investigations into ring-stiffened cylindrical shells provide valuable insights for determining the ideal buckling resistance of these structures under external pressure loading. For this purpose, one of the following approaches can be utilized:

- *Discrete consideration of ring stiffeners (e.g. Kendrick (20), (21), Ross (22), Salerno/Levine (23), Singer/Haftka (24)),*
- *Smearing method (e.g. Flügge (25), Geier (26), (27), Singer et al. (28), Soong (29)),*
- *Approximate treatment using an engineering assumption (e.g. Brayant's formula in (30)).*

Theoretical models are powerful tools for analyzing the buckling behaviour of ring-stiffened shells. However, their accuracy relies on assumptions and simplifications that may not fully capture real complexities in the buckling behaviour of these structures. Experimental investigations bridge this gap by providing real-world data to validate these models and identify potential limitations.

While past research has focused on ring-stiffened cylindrical shells made from carbon steel (as shown in Fig. 3), a significant knowledge gap exists for shells made from high-strength structural steels and duplex stainless steels. The influence of their material-specific properties, particularly the non-linear stress-strain behaviour of duplex stainless steel, on the buckling behaviour remains unexplored.

Fig. 3. Buckling test results on ring-stiffened circular cylinder shells from (31) in comparison to the buckling capacity curves of EN 1993-1-6 for fabrication tolerance quality classes (FQC) A, B and C

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

2.1 General

Within the German IGF research project 21719 N and further research activities conducted at the Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures at the University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany (IML-UDE), experimental and numerical investigations as well as an extensive literature review into the buckling behaviour of externally loaded shells were carried out and explained in the following. Besides, the Steel and Lightweight Construction Research Institute for Steel, Wood and Stone at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) has conducted investigations into the buckling behaviour of axially compressed cylindrical shells. The experimental investigations of IML-UDE comprise six buckling tests on circumferentially loaded cylindrical shells made of duplex stainless steel with nominal dimensions of $r = 500$ mm, $t = 0.5$ mm, and $l = 978$ mm, see *Table 1*. These experimental tests can be divided into three two categories: (i) unstiffened cylindrical shells and (ii) ring stiffened shells. The test data obtained from buckling tests on unstiffened cylindrical shells lead to the determination of the increase in buckling capacity due to ring stiffeners.

Table 1. Buckling tests on circumferentially loaded cylindrical shells made of duplex (1.4162) stainless steel

Test	Steel grade	Dimension of cylinders	Dimension of stiffeners	relative slenderness
		$r / t / l$ ¹⁾	$n_{st} / b_{st} / t_{st}$ ²⁾	$\bar{\lambda}$ ³⁾
		[mm]	[mm]	[-]
U1-LDX-0.5-0	Duplex stainless steel (1.4162)	500 / 0.5 / 978	—	11.5
U2-LDX-0.5-0			—	
U3-LDX-0.5-1			1 / 15 / 1	11.5
U4-LDX-0.5-1				
U5-LDX-0.5-2			2 / 15 / 1	11.5
U6-LDX-0.5-2				

¹⁾ Radius (r), wall thickness (t), length (l). | ²⁾ Number of stiffeners (n_{st}), stiffener width (b_{st}), stiffener thickness (t_{st}). | ³⁾ relative slenderness of the shell specimen.

This paper presents the results of buckling tests on specimens U1-LDX-0.5-0 (without ring stiffness) and U3-LDX-0.5-1 (with one ring stiffness).

2.2 Manufacturing and testing procedure

The test specimens, fabricated from 0.5 mm thick duplex stainless steel sheet (1.4162), were formed into cylinders using a hand-rolling process. This manufacturing method was chosen due to very low thickness of the sheets and to minimize the imperfections that could influence the buckling behaviour. Following the rolling process, the longitudinal seam was joined using adhesive bonding and bolting. To reproduce the realistic behaviour of shell structures during testing, rings were affixed to both the top and bottom edges of the shells (see *Fig. 4*), ensuring the circular form is maintained at these crucial points. Notably, the top ring is bolted to the upper circular plate to transfer the tensile force generated by the weight through the ring, thereby avoiding localized stress concentration at the cylinder edge. Following fabrication, the cylindrical shell underwent a leakage test to identify and seal any potential openings using adhesive. Subsequently, a vacuum pump was employed to extract air from the shell, creating internal vacuum pressure, as illustrated in *Fig. 4*.

Prior to testing, all specimens underwent initial imperfection measurements using a 3D camera measurement system (ARAMIS GOM) (see *Fig. 5*). This involved precisely positioning each shell and capturing its outer surface geometry with the system.

Out-of-roundness for all specimens remained within the established tolerance limits for fabrication quality class A according to EN 1993-1-6. Additionally, due to the selected manufacturing process, the tested shells exhibited minimal deviations in the circumferential direction, thereby meeting the initial dimple parameter requirements specified for fabrication quality tolerance class A in the same standard.

Fig. 4. Manufacturing process of test specimens for buckling tests on cylindrical shells made of stainless steel

The test specimens were loaded at constant speed rate until they reached their maximum deformation capacity and developed a leak due to large deformation. Circumferential pressure was applied and the deformations were recorded using a 3D camera measurement system (ARAMIS GOM). Simultaneously, an internal pressure measurement system monitored the pressure within the shells. Once the maximum deformation was reached, the load was reduced until the shell returned to its initial deformation state. Following the completion of the tests, all specimens were re-measured to quantify any permanent deformations that may have occurred.

Fig. 5. Characterization of initial geometric imperfections using a 3D camera measurement System

2.3 Evaluation and discussion of the buckling test results

Fig. 6 presents the experimental load-deformation behaviour of two cylindrical shells subjected to external pressure: (i) test specimen U1-LDX-0.5-0 without ring stiffener and (ii) test specimen U3-LDX-0.5-1 with one ring stiffener in the middle length. Both shells have identical geometries to ensure comparability.

Fig. 6. Load-deformation behaviour of two duplex (1.4162) stainless steel specimens under uniform external pressure

The results shown in Fig. 6 clearly demonstrate that the stiffened shell exhibits a significantly higher load-carrying capacity, with an approximate 35% increase compared to the unstiffened shell. Additionally, the presence of the stiffener noticeably reduces the deformations in both the pre-buckling and post-buckling regions. This enhancement is attributed to the altered buckling pattern induced by the stiffener. The ring stiffener effectively divides the global buckling mode of the unstiffened cylindrical shell into two localized buckling regions, one above and one below the stiffener (see Fig. 7), leading to the observed improvements in strength and reduced deformations.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the first buckling modes for unstiffened and ring-stiffened cylindrical shells under internal vacuum (uniform external pressure)

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 General

Experimental testing can be costly, time-consuming, and limited in terms of the range of parameters that can be investigated. For this reason, numerical simulations offer a cost-effective and efficient alternative to experimental testing. For this purpose, the accuracy of the FE model must be verified by comparing its predicted buckling loads with those obtained from controlled laboratory buckling tests. This validation process ensures the reliability of the FE model for applying beyond the range of experimental data. This subsection compares the results of linear and nonlinear buckling analyses with those obtained from experimental buckling tests and analytical predictions from EN 1993-1-6. All linear and nonlinear buckling analyses were performed using the FE program ANSYS APDL R23.1 (32). For nonlinear analyses involving imperfect cylindrical shells, the arc-length method was employed. This technique, widely used for nonlinear buckling analysis of shell structures (e.g. (33)-(37)), allows for capturing the complete load-displacement response of the investigated shells.

Simply supported boundary conditions (BC1f and BC2f) were applied at both top and bottom edges of the cylindrical shells, as defined in (1). However, the loaded edge exhibited coupled degrees of freedom (see (35)). This means all points at the top edge were connected through a reference point, allowing for both transverse and meridional displacements.

To determine an optimal mesh density for each shell geometry, a series of linear buckling analyses (LBA) and geometrically nonlinear analyses (GNA) were conducted on perfect cylindrical shells. The FE models were progressively refined until the predicted buckling loads for each shell geometry converged.

All shell models were meshed with four-node shell elements (element type 181) with six degrees of freedom per node. The suitability of this element type was confirmed by comparing the numerical bifurcation loads with analytical results (see (34), (35)). This element type has also been shown effective in previous studies by the authors (34)-(37) for predicting buckling behaviour of cylindrical shells under various loading conditions.

3.2 Comparing numerical and experimental results

Experimental and numerical results are compared for externally loaded test specimens. The buckling capacities were determined by laboratory tests ($R_{EXP.}$), GMNIA analyses (R_{GMNIA}) and analytical expressions of EN 1993-1-6 ($R_{EN\ 1993-1-6}$). Additionally, the critical elastic buckling resistances of the test specimens were determined analytically according to EN 1993-1-6 ($R_{Cr,EN\ 1993-1-6}$) and numerically using LBA analyses (R_{LBA}).

A linear buckling analysis (LBA), also known as an eigenvalue analysis, can be used to determine the elastic critical buckling resistance (R_{Cr}) of the entire shell structure or individual parts like segments or strakes. An LBA analysis was initially applied to the tested shell geometry with the results subsequently compared to EN 1993-1-6 to assess its validity.

The comparison of the LBA results with the linear buckling pressure calculated using the EN 1993-1-6 formulae for unstiffened cylindrical shells reveals a good correlation, see *Table 2*. This finding suggests:

- *The accuracy of the FE model: The agreement between the FE model's predictions (LBA) and the established analytical method (EN 1993-1-6) provides confidence in the FE model's ability to capture the linear buckling behaviour of the shells.*
- *The reliability of the EN 1993-1-6 approach: The good correlation also supports the validity of the analytical method prescribed in EN 1993-1-6 for predicting the buckling pressure of similar unstiffened shells.*

The geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis, which explicitly included imperfections (GMNIA), also yielded acceptable agreement between the FE results and the test results. However, some discrepancies were observed:

- *Unstiffened Shell (U1-LDX-0.5-0): The FE model (R_{GMNIA}) slightly underestimated the load-bearing capacity of the unstiffened shell.*

- *Ring-Stiffened Shell (U1-LDX-0.5-0): Conversely, the model overestimated the load-bearing capacity of ring-stiffened shells.*

The above observed discrepancies are most probably due to the lack of implementation of measured geometric imperfections of test specimens and measured stress-strain curves from tensile tests in the FE models. These features will be incorporated in future refinements to improve the accuracy of the simulations.

Table 2. Comparison of the buckling test results with numerical and analytical calculations for circumferentially loaded cylindrical shells made of duplex (1.4162) stainless steel

Test	R_{LBA}	$R_{cr,EN 1993-1-6}$	$R_{EN1993-1-6}$ (FQC A)	R_{GMNIA} (FQC A)	$R_{Exp.}$
	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]
U1-LDX-0.5-0	3.72×10^{-3}	3.71×10^{-3}	2.78×10^{-3}	3.21×10^{-3}	3.53×10^{-3}
U3-LDX-0.5-1	6.68×10^{-3}	–	5.01×10^{-3}	5.58×10^{-3}	3.18×10^{-3}

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper presents first combined numerical and experimental investigations of unstiffened and ring-stiffened circular cylinder shells subjected to circumferential pressure. The key findings are as follows:

- *Experimental testing demonstrated an approximately 35% increase in load capacity for the cylindrical shell with a ring stiffener compared to the unstiffened shell.*
- *Linear elastic bifurcation analysis (LBA) showed good agreement with analytical predictions from EN 1993-1-6, indicating the model's ability to predict ideal elastic buckling loads.*
- *Geometrically and materially nonlinear analysis (GMNIA) revealed the need to incorporate measured imperfections and stress-strain curves into the FE models for improved agreement with experimental results.*

A subsequent publication will present the findings of further tests and refined FE calculations incorporating these influential factors, aiming to achieve closer agreement between numerical and experimental results.

The authors would like to thank the German Federation of Industrial Research Associations (AiF) and the Research Association for Steel Application (FOSTA) for funding the research project P 1510/IGF-No. 21719 N “Load bearing behaviour of meridionally and ring stiffened tanks and silos made of high strength (duplex) steels and low-temperature steels for pressure vessels”.

REFERENCES

1. **EN 1993-1-6:2007 + AC:2009 + A1:2017:** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – *Part 1-6: Strength and stability of shell structures.*
2. **Rotter, J.M., Schmidt, H.** 2013 (EDS.) *Buckling of steel shells, European design recommendations.* 5th Edition, Revised 2nd impression. ECCS-European Convention for Constructional Steelwork.
3. **DIN EN 10088-4:2010-01:** Stainless steels – *Part 4: Technical delivery conditions for sheet/plate and strip of corrosion resisting steels for construction purposes.*
4. **DIN EN 10088-5: 2009-07:** Stainless steels – *Part 5: Technical delivery conditions for bars, rods, wire, sections and bright products of corrosion resisting steels for construction purposes.*
5. **EN 1993-4-1: 2017-09:** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – *Part 4-1: Silos.*
6. **EN 1993-4-2: 2017-09:** Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – *Part 4-2: Tanks.*
7. **Rules for the design, construction and inspection of offshore structures,** 1977: Appendix / Det Norske Veritas; C: Steel structures, Hovik, 1982.

8. **American Society of Mechanical Engineers: ASME**, *Boiler and pressure vessels code* – Section III, Code case N – 284. New York: ASME 1980.
9. **von Mises, R.** *Der kritische Außenbeuldruck für allseits belastete Rohre*, Stodola Festschrift (1929), p. 418-430.
10. **Windenburg, D. F., Trilling, C.** *Collapse by Instability of Thin Cylindrical Shells under External Pressure*, Trans. ASME 50 (1934), No. 11.
11. **Batdorf, S.B.** *A Simplified Method of Elastic-Stability Analysis for Thin Cylindrical Shells*, NACA TN No. 1341 (1947).
12. **Schnell, W.** *Einfluss der Randvorverwölbung auf die Beulwerte von Zylinderschalen unter Manteldruck*. Der Stahlbau 6 (1965), p. 187-190.
13. **Singer, J.** *The Effect of Axial Constraint on The Instability of Thin Circular Cylindrical Shells Under External Pressure*, Jour. of Appl. Mech. 27 (1960) p. 737-739.
14. **Thielemann, W.F., Esslinger, M.** *Einfluss der Randbedingungen auf die Beullast von Kreiszyinderschalen*, Der Stahlbau 12 (1964), p. 353-361.
15. **Greiner, R.** *Ein baustatisches Lösungsverfahren zur Beulberechnung dünnwandiger Kreiszyinderschalen unter Manteldruck*. Bauingenieur-Praxis Heft 17 (1972).
16. **Azizi, E., Stranghöner, N.** *Sensitivity of unstiffened cylindrical shells under external pressure*, Proceedings of Eurosteel 2021 Conference, Sheffield, United Kingdom, ce/papers 4 (2021), Issue 2-4, p. 1789-1796.
17. **Donnell, L.H.** *Effect of Imperfection on Buckling of Thin Cylinders with Fixed Edges under External Pressure*, Proc. 3rd US Nat. Congr. App. Mech. (1958), ASME, p. 305-311.
18. **Hutchinson, J.W.** *Buckling of Imperfect Cylindrical Shells under Axial Compression and External Pressure*. AIAA jour, Vol. 6 (1962), No. 12, p. 2301-2305.
19. **Knoedel, P. Ummenhofer, T., Rotter, J. M.** *Rethinking Imperfections in Tanks and Silos*, Eurosteel 2017, 8th European Conf. on Steel and Composite Structures. 15-17 September 2017, Copenhagen, Denmark, ce/papers 1 (2017), Issue 2-3, p. 960-969.
20. **Kendrick, S.** *The Buckling under External Pressure of circular cylindrical Shells with Evenly Spaced, Equal Strength, Circular Ring Frames – Part I: NCRE Repot No. R211 (1953).*
21. **Kendrick, S.** *The Buckling under External Pressure of circular cylindrical Shells with Evenly Spaced, Equal Strength, Circular Ring Frames – Part II: NCRE Repot No. R211 (1953).*
22. **Ross, C.T.F.** *The Collapse of Ring-Reinforced Cylinders Under Uniform External Pressure*, Trans. Roy. Inst. Naval Arch., RINA 107 (1965), p. 375-394.
23. **Salerno, V. L., Levine, B.** *General Instability of Reinforced Shells under Hydrostatic Pressure*, Polytechnic Inst. Brooklyn, New York, PIBAL Rep. No. 189 (1951).
24. **Singer, J., Haftka, R.** *Buckling of Discretely Ring-Stiffened Cylindrical Shells*, TAE Report No. 67, 1968.
25. **Flügge, W.** *Die Stabilität der Kreiszyinderschalen*, Ingenieure-Archive Berlin 3 (1932), p. 463-506.
26. **Geiger, B.** *Das Beulverhalten versteifter Zylinderschalen – Teil 1: Differenzialgleichungen*, Zschrft. Flugwiss. 14 (1966), H.7, p. 306-323.
27. **Geiger, B.** *Beullasten versteifter Kreiszyinderschalen*, Jahresbuch der WGLR (1965), p. 440-447.
28. **Singer, J., Baruch, M., Harari, O.** *Further Remarks on The Effect of Eccentricity of Stiffeners on The General Instability of Stiffened Cylindrical Shells*. TAE Report No. 42 (1965).
29. **Soong, T.C.** *Buckling of Cylindrical Shell Under Pressure by Using Sanders' Theory*. AIAA Jour. Vol. 5 (1967), No. 5, p. 1049-1052.
30. **Brayant, A.R.** *Hydrostatic Pressure Buckling of a Ringstiffened Tube*. NCRE Report No. R306 (1954).
31. **Düsing, I. E.** *Stabilität stählerner ringversteifter Kreiszyinderschalen unter allseitig konstantem Außendruck*, Universität GH Essen, Dissertation, 1998.
32. **ANSYS Mechanical APDL**, Version 23.1.

33. **Wang, J., Sadowski, A.J.** *Elastic imperfect tip-loaded cantilever cylinders of varying length*. International Journal of Mechanical Sciences 140, p. 200–210, 2018.
34. **Azizi, E., Stranghöner, N.** *Imperfection sensitivity of unstiffened cylindrical shells under external pressure*. Proceedings of Eurosteel 2021 Conference, Sheffield, United Kingdom, ce/papers 4 (2021), Issue 2-4, p. 1789–1796.
35. **Azizi, E., Stranghöner, N.** *Imperfection sensitivity of cylindrical shells under shear loading*, The International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures, Aveiro, Portugal, 14-16, September, 2022, p. 685-692.
36. **Stranghöner, N., Azizi, E., Gorbachov, A.** *Influence of material nonlinearity on the buckling resistance of stainless steel shells*. Journal of Constructional Steel Research 157, p. 386–396, 2019.
37. **Azizi, E., Stranghöner, N.** *Buckling of externally pressured cylinders with different degrees of ring-stiffening*. Proceedings of the XIV International Conference on Metal Structures (ICMS'2021), Poznań, Poland, June 16-18, 2021, online conference, p. 265-271.